

DIRECTIONS D1.1:

Report describing optimisation model on DC system design for offshore energy hubs considering extendability, redundancy needs, and protection requirements

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Contributors: G. Bastianel, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun.

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Contents

1	Executive summary	1
2	Introduction and motivation	5
3	Planning methodology for electrical energy hubs	7
3.1	General structure of the planning methodology	8
3.2	Topology optimisation model	10
4	Application of the planning methodology	13
4.1	Extendability	13
4.2	Redundancy needs	13
4.3	Protection requirements	15
4.4	Unbalanced operation of HVDC grids	16
4.5	Risk-based assessment of operational benefits	16
4.6	Summary	17
	Bibliography	19

Chapter 1

Executive summary

The European Union's commitment to decarbonising its power system is expected to drive a substantial increase in installed offshore wind capacity in the North Sea by 2050, accompanied by a number of announced multi-terminal and meshed High-Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) projects. Compared with point-to-point interconnections, multi-terminal HVDC grids allow power to be exchanged between DC substations and thereby raise the inherent redundancy of the system, while offering operational flexibility to mitigate congestion through power-flow control and topological actions. This deliverable (D1.1, produced within Task 1.1 of the DIRECTIONS project) reports on a planning methodology, and the optimisation model at its core, developed to quantify these benefits and to support planning decisions on offshore electrical energy hubs.

Objective The methodology determines, for a given set of candidate grid *layouts* and substation *configurations* (inputs), the optimal *topology* (output) of an electrical energy hub under a range of operating conditions, including varying renewable injections and system congestion. The goal is to express the value of each design option in terms of operational cost savings or increased renewable energy integration, addressing five design aspects:

- **Extendability** — accommodating future transmission and generation additions with minimal connection effort;
- **Redundancy needs** — the transmission capacity required to avoid load curtailment under faults;
- **Protection requirements** — safe operation under electrical faults, modelled as additional constraints;
- **Unbalanced operation of HVDC grids** — behaviour of monopolar, symmetrical-monopolar, and bipolar configurations after single-pole

outages;

- **Risk-based quantification** — weighting operating conditions by likelihood and accounting for operational flexibility under uncertainty.

Methodology and model The heart of the methodology is a topology optimisation model implemented as the open-source library `PowerModelsTopologicalActions.jl`. The model selects the optimal switching state of all switching units, and the associated splitting or merging of AC and DC busbars, to minimise operating cost (equivalently, to maximise renewable energy injection via a merit-order dispatch). It is subject to the power-flow equations (Ohm's and Kirchhoff's laws), operational limits of all grid elements, and satisfaction of demand. Each busbar can be split into two parts linked by a zero-impedance line, with connected elements routed to either part through discrete switching variables, extending a classical hybrid AC/DC optimal power flow formulation.

Input data comprise generation costs, demand and renewable time series (e.g., from ENTSO-E's TYNDP 2024), consistently modelled cross-border exchanges, and network layout, configuration, and impedance data including the planning candidates under comparison.

Key finding Because analysing many layouts, configurations, and operating conditions requires hundreds of thousands of calculations, several mathematical formulations were compared for accuracy and speed: the nonlinear nonconvex (AC), second-order cone (SOC), quadratic convex (QC), and Linear Programming Approximation (LPAC). The LPAC formulation, which preserves information on voltage and reactive power flows, provides sufficient accuracy while reducing computational time by roughly two orders of magnitude, making large-scale comparative studies tractable.

Application and next steps The methodology will be applied to test cases in Work Package 4, notably the Princess Elisabeth energy island, to identify the configuration yielding the lowest operational cost when future offshore wind extensions and interconnections are connected. Redundancy is illustrated through single- versus double-busbar DC configurations, and protection strategies (e.g., preventive line opening versus DC circuit breakers) are encoded as explicit constraints so that their socio-economic value can be compared. In Task 1.3, the optimiser will be further extended to determine optimal topologies while accounting for forecast errors in renewable generation and demand, yielding a more accurate basis for cost-benefit and investment analysis.

This deliverable's content is based on the following paper currently under review:

- G. Bastianel, M. Vanin, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, "Optimal Transmission Switching and Busbar Splitting in Hybrid AC/DC Grids.", *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, 2026, 102182, ISSN 2352-4677, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segan.2026.102182>.

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Chapter 2

Introduction and motivation

Due to the European Union's commitment to decarbonize its power system, a massive increase in installed offshore wind capacity is expected in the North Sea by 2050 [1]. In conjunction with the offshore wind investments, several offshore multi-terminal and meshed High-Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) projects in the North Sea area have been announced [2]. Multi-terminal HVDC grids allow the exchange of power between different DC substations, inherently increasing the system's redundancy compared to having only point-to-point HVDC interconnections. HVDC systems can provide operational flexibility for mitigating congestion based on their chosen configuration. This can be provided by means of power flow control by changing the set point of HVDC converters, and by performing topological actions in the offshore grids. The aim of *DIRECTIONS* is to develop a planning methodology to quantify such benefits while determining the best combination of grid layout, and configurations (see next chapter for exact definitions), considering the aspects of:

- Extendability
- Redundancy needs
- Protection system requirements
- Unbalanced operation of HVDC grids
- Risk-based quantification of operational benefits

The next chapter outlines the planning methodology and explains how the methodology can be used to analyse different grid layouts and configurations with respect to the aspects listed above. The heart of the planning methodology is an optimisation model that allows for optimising the topology of the system under different operating conditions. The final chapter explains how the existing methodology will be applied to a variety of test cases within the course of work package 4 of *DIRECTIONS*.

Chapter 3

Planning methodology for electrical energy hubs

The developed planning methodology aims to identify the benefits in terms of operational cost savings or an increase in the amount of renewable energy integration for a given set of grid layouts and configurations (input) for an electrical energy hub by identifying its optimal topology (output) under different operating conditions, e.g., RES injections, system loading conditions, and N-1 contingencies. Firstly, the terms layout, configuration, and topology are defined in the following paragraph as also illustrated in Figure 3.1.

- **Electrical energy hub (EEH):** is a multifunctional node in a power system, managed separately from the main existing control areas, which aggregates local GW-size electrical generation capacities in a compact geographical area. It is characterized by a high density of electrical equipment and has multiple interconnections to existing control areas. The Princess Elisabeth energy island is an EEH [3].
- **Layout:** refers to the high-level design of the grid, i.e., which busbars in the grid are connected, which technology is used (AC or DC), and what the voltage level and power rating of each of the connection paths is (Figure 3.1 - left). In terms of power system modelling, this corresponds to a bus-branch model as commonly used in single line diagrams (SLDs) [4].
- **Configuration:** refers to the possible arrangement of the network elements located in a substation as depicted in Figure 3.1 - centre. Each considered system layout can have multiple configurations, consisting of different bus bar arrangements (single, double, triple, horizontal or vertical splitting), and the number of circuit breakers and disconnectors utilised. Especially in the context of multi-terminal and meshed

Figure 3.1: Terminology used in the planning methodology. Layout (left), configuration (center), and topology (right).

HVDC grids, where the cost of circuit breakers is substantial, it is important to assess the benefits of a given configuration for a robust cost-benefit analysis. In the literature, the models representing the specific configuration of the system are referred to as bus-breaker models [4].

- **Topology** refers to the actual switching state of a given network configuration at a given time point, i.e., operating condition as shown at the right-hand side of Figure 3.1. Each configuration thus can result in several different topologies, which can be determined by the grid operator based on the operational state of the grid (loading conditions, cross-border flows, N-1 contingencies, etc.). As such, system operators can minimise the operating cost of the system, i.e., maximise the amount of renewable energy injection by selecting the best possible topology.

3.1 General structure of the planning methodology

The proposed planning methodology consists of selecting the optimal topology among a set of possible configurations for a given set of system layouts. The principle of the method shown in Figure 3.2 outlines the steps to select the final topology. By using layout and configuration information as input, and optimising the topology for several different credible operating states, we can compare layouts and their corresponding configurations in terms of operational benefits, allowing us to make a robust investment decision. The heart of the methodology is an optimisation model (and tool) developed as part of *DIRECTIONS* - Task 1.1, which will be briefly discussed in this document. The full mathematical description of the model and its implementation is provided in [5] and is online available under [this link](#).

The following paragraphs outline the input data that is used in the topology optimiser to determine the operational benefits for different layouts and configurations:

Figure 3.2: Steps of the planning methodology described in the deliverable.

- **Layout and configuration inputs:** pre-determined layouts and configurations (a set of planning candidates) for optimising their topology under different operating conditions. The decision variables are represented by switching units, which can be open or closed.
- **Topology outputs:** the topology optimiser model outputs the status (open/closed) of the several switching units included in the predetermined configurations used as inputs. Together with the status of the switching units, the power flow through the AC and DC branches of the hybrid AC/DC grids, the voltage magnitudes and angles, and the converter and generator set points for a given operating condition are computed by the model for a specified objective, e.g., minimum generation (re)dispatch cost, minimum RES curtailment etc.
- **Input data - Operating conditions:** numerical parameters which are used by the model to compute the optimal value of all the variables in the model. The data used as input for the optimization model are:
 - **Generation costs:** each generator type is assigned a fixed cost per generated MWh. Overall, the model’s objective is to minimize generation costs, i.e., the operational cost of the system. However, as generation costs are highly volatile and unpredictable with respect to the long-term future, the objective of the optimisation is formulated as maximising the amount of renewable energy injection into the system, or minimising RES curtailment. For this purpose, a merit order of different generator types is created, which represents a hierarchy in the dispatch decisions in which renewables get the highest priority.
 - **Demand time series:** Generator dispatch and system topology are determined such that the demand in the system is met under all considered loading conditions. A possible example of such demand profiles is the hourly demand time series of ENTSO-E’s

Ten-Year Network Development Plan 2024, providing an hourly aggregated demand for each market zone in Europe, which is obtained from the dataset [6].

- **RES time series:** Similar to demand, also renewable energy production time series needs to be considered to account for the variability of RES generation. In this respect, it is important that the correlation between available renewable generation and power demand due to weather conditions is considered in an accurate way. One source of such data is the ENTSO-E’s TYNDP 2024 data [6] set, providing the hourly capacity factor for onshore wind, offshore wind, and solar PV for each market zone in Europe.
- **Cross-border exchanges:** Especially when isolating a specific region of the power grid to do a detailed topological analysis, the power exchanges between neighbouring zones should be consistently modelled such that the net position of a given zone does not change after topological remedial actions are applied. One approach that can be used in the European context is to first compute interconnection flows on ENTSO-E’s zonal model, including one node per market zone in Europe. When running the topological optimization model for selected market zones (for a tractable solution), the net transfer capacities through the interconnecting lines can be fixed to the outcome of the zonal model.
- **Network data:** includes the layout, configuration, and impedance data of the existing network, which is extended by the different planning candidates considered (and compared). The input data model used within *DIRECTIONS* is described under [7] and [8].

3.2 Topology optimisation model

As introduced in the previous sections, the developed optimisation model aims at determining the optimal topology of the system, under a given operating condition, e.g., the switching state of transmission lines and the potential splitting or merging of different busbars for AC and DC substations. Mathematically, this problem can be formulated in a variety of forms, which all result in different computational performance. Note that to analyse a variety of grid layouts, configurations, and operating conditions, many (several hundreds of thousands) calculations are required. To that end, in *DIRECTIONS* we compare (nonlinear nonconvex (AC), second-order cone (SOC), quadratic convex (QC), and the Linear Programming Approximation (LPAC) formulations in terms of accuracy and computational speed [5]. The optimisation model, including all mentioned mathematical formulations, is im-

plemented as an open-source software library [PowerModelsTopologicalActions.jl](#).

The objective of the optimisation model is to find the most cost-effective operating state of the system as introduced in the previous section. The optimisation constraints are:

- Power flow equations, e.g., Ohm's and Kirchhoff's laws
- Operational limits (power rating and voltage range) of all grid elements, such as lines, cables, transformers, HVDC converters, generators, etc.
- Satisfaction of the demand

Figures 3.3 and 3.4 show respectively how different substation configurations are represented in the developed optimisation model. The model introduces several discrete variables representing AC and DC switching elements. In the optimisation model, each AC and/or DC busbar in a given configuration can be split or merged, where the splitting/merging decision is taken by the optimiser. When split, the busbar is divided into two parts, linked by a zero impedance line. Each network element connected to the original split busbar can be connected to the two parts via two switching units, one for each part of the split busbar. Besides all the decision variables of a classical optimal power flow (OPF) model for hybrid AC/DC grids [8], the developed model thus provides the optimal combination of topologies in each modelled substation, as shown in Figure 3.4 (0 \rightarrow open, 1 \rightarrow closed).

Figure 3.3: AC and DC switch models for busbar splitting.

The performance of the different formulations has been compared in terms of accuracy and computational speed. The results show that the Linear Programming Approximation [9] (LPAC) approximation of the AC-OPF, which preserves information on the system voltage and reactive power flows (as

Figure 3.4: Busbar splitting representation with AC and DC switching units for AC and DC busbars. Each grid element originally connected to the split busbars is attached to an auxiliary bus and linked to each part of the split busbar through a switch.

opposed to the standard “DC” linear approximation used in the literature [7]) provides sufficient accuracy with a decrease in computational time of about two orders of magnitude which will allow us to compare a variety of layouts and configurations within work package 4 of *DIRECTIONS*.

Chapter 4

Application of the planning methodology

As anticipated in Chapter 3.2, the planning methodology determines the most efficient topology of a given power system by selecting the optimal switching states of all switching units for different operating conditions. This chapter elaborates on the application of the planning methodology to specific aspects of Electrical Energy Hub design, namely *extendability*, *redundancy needs*, and *protection requirements*, *unbalanced operation of HVDC grids* and *risk-based assessment of operational benefits*.

4.1 Extendability

Extendability is interpreted as foreseeing and evaluating the possibility of adding several transmission lines and/or generation capacity to a given power system in the future, with a minimum of effort to connect these.

Using the methodology described in Section 3.1, and the topology optimiser [5], we will identify which of the possible configurations of the Princess Elizabeth Island results in the lowest operational costs if future offshore wind extensions and interconnections as envisaged by Entso-e's (TYNDP) [6] and Elia's electricity system blueprint 2035-2050 [10] are connected to the Princess Elizabeth Island. Furthermore, the additional available transfer capacity throughout the grid can be computed, and potential additional expansion options explored.

4.2 Redundancy needs

The *redundancy needs* of a power system can be expressed as the transmission capacity needed for power to be transferred to demand centers while

avoiding load curtailment, even in the case of electrical faults occurring. It can be assessed by means of contingency analysis for a given set of $(N-1)$ or generally $(N-x)$ contingencies, where faulted network elements are removed from the grid. By performing power flow calculations for the contingencies, potential overloading situations are identified, which can lead to generation or demand curtailment. Furthermore, using optimal power flow calculations, one can identify re-dispatching needs under contingency conditions to avoid demand shedding. In systems with higher redundancy, potential redispatch and curtailment needs will be less than in systems with lower redundancy. Using the topology optimiser, we can thus compare different configurations with a variety of redundant elements and how they improve the performance of the system, i.e., by reducing demand curtailment and re-dispatching cost. Therefore, the developed topology optimiser allows us to select the best configuration for each substation considered as a planning candidate, taking into account contingencies. Moreover, the topology optimiser is useful for evaluating the necessary number of busbars, switching units, and parallel cables that one needs to install to guarantee a redundant system.

Figure 4.1: Two possible configurations for a DC busbar connecting four different AC/DC converters: single DC busbar (left) versus double DC busbar (right).

The principle of the analysis is outlined with a simple example as shown in Figure 4.1. On the one hand, a single busbar configuration (Figure 4.1-left) leads to a simpler (and less expensive) configuration, but the DC grid cannot transfer power if a fault happens in one of the HVDC links. On the other hand, on the right-hand side of Figure 4.1, a double busbar configuration guarantees more redundancy and the possibility of isolating the faulted HVDC link while still transferring power over the other lines connected to the second busbar. Given that the optimization model uses generation costs

as an input, the economic benefit brought by having a more redundant configuration can be computed. This information allows, e.g., transmission system operators to evaluate the benefits brought by each configuration and make an informed choice on the substation topologies to be installed.

4.3 Protection requirements

When planning substation configurations, the grid must be guaranteed to operate safely in case of electrical faults. Different types of protection devices can be represented by adding different types of constraints to the switching units previously presented in Figure 3.3. For example, a variable (and an associated constraint) representing the current through a switching unit can be added to limit the short-circuit current in case of faults. Furthermore, based on the power transfer capacity of both the AC and DC parts of a hybrid AC/DC grid and especially the layout of the DC grid, the most appropriate protection strategy [11] can be selected to avoid having a loss of in-feed lower than the dimensioning incident of the power system. The five-terminal HVDC grid illustrated in Figure 4.2 can preventively open line L_5 if the power being transmitted is foreseen to be above the dimensioning incident of the power system. At the same time, the benefits to the socioeconomic welfare brought by the two protection devices can be computed to select which is the best for a given test case.

Figure 4.2: Five-terminal HVDC grid with parallel point-to-point connection

Hence, different protection strategies can be explicitly modelled through mathematical constraints and added to the topology optimiser. As a result, the busbar splitting actions can be optimised considering their effect on pro-

tection devices, thus directly adding *protection requirements* to the planning of the different substation topologies.

4.4 Unbalanced operation of HVDC grids

One of the important design aspects for HVDC grids is the choice of the particular configuration of the HVDC system. Generally, HVDC systems can be realised in monopolar, symmetrical monopolar or bipolar configurations [12]. The power transfer capability of the HVDC grid after isolation of faulty system elements is determined by the particular configuration of the HVDC grid [12]. Especially, bipolar HVDC grids, with a dedicated metallic return conductor, offer a higher transfer capacity after single pole outages as only the parts of the system that are faulty need to be taken out of service, whereas for (symmetrical) monopoles often also healthy parts need to be taken out of operation [13]. In bipolar HVDC grids, after single pole outages, the system is operated in an unbalanced way, and the amount of system unbalance that could be handled depends on the grid layout and DC substation configurations, which determine the power flows and DC grid voltages in the system. As such, the topology optimiser developed within *DIRECTIONS* can be utilised in combination with the optimal power flow tool for unbalanced DC grid operation as provided in [14], to analyse the operational benefits of the HVDC system configurations together with the different DC substation configurations.

4.5 Risk-based assessment of operational benefits

As mentioned in the previous sections, the developed planning methodology compares different system layouts and configurations for a number of different operating conditions, both during normal operation and after contingencies. A risk-based assessment is needed for robust decision-making to quantify the operational benefits of each layout and configuration. In this context, risk can be considered in two fundamental ways.

Firstly, not all operating conditions have the same likelihood. Therefore, the likelihood of each operating condition should be taken into account when determining the benefits under different operating conditions. This can be done using a weighted sum approach using probability values for the different operating conditions when determining the cumulative benefits over a given planning horizon.

Secondly, the flexibility provided by each layout and configuration might impact the operational decision-making under uncertainty. During system operation, topological remedial actions are determined ahead of time, and as

such, they are subject to uncertainty due to forecast errors in renewable energy generation and demand. Configurations offering higher flexibility result in lower operational costs as a wider range of preventive and corrective actions is available than in configurations with lower flexibility. As such, by determining the set of topological actions while simultaneously considering forecast errors, we can have a more accurate representation of operational benefits, which eventually serve as input for investment decisions. As such, within task 1.3 of *DIRECTIONS*, the topology optimizer as introduced in Section 3.2 will be further extended to determine the optimal system topology considering forecast errors observed in the operational time frame.

4.6 Summary

The chapter has outlined how the aspects of *extendability*, *redundancy needs*, *protection requirements*, *unbalanced DC grid operation* and *risk-based assessment of operational benefits* will be covered within the developed planning methodology, mainly utilising the topology optimiser developed within *DIRECTIONS* [5]. While extendability and redundancy needs are dependent on the grid layout and the RES and load time series for a given time instance, therefore being *scenario-based*, the protection requirements are related to a *set of additional constraints* to be added to the topology optimisation model. The aspect of unbalanced DC grid operation, can be covered together with the system redundancy needs as both the HVDC system and DC substation configurations play a role. Finally, it is important to model decisions on the system topology for a given configuration and layout under uncertainty to obtain a more accurate input for conducting a cost-benefit analysis.

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